

Induced Currents on an EUT in a Free-Space and a Modified TEM Cell Environment

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Abstract

The finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method is used to investigate whether the currents induced on an equipment under test (EUT) in a TEM cell are similar to those induced in an ideal free-space environment. The approach is to simulate an identical EUT in both environments and determine a correlation based on the respective current distributions. The effect of the EUT size relative to the TEM cell as compared to free space is also investigated.

Keywords

Numerical simulation, transverse electromagnetic cell.

INTRODUCTION

Transverse electromagnetic (TEM) cells are used to simulate a free-space plane wave for probe calibrations, emission and immunity testing, and other EMC applications. In the immunity test case, the goal is to electrically "stress" the EUT as would a plane-wave in an ideal free space environment. This paper examines this goal by considering numerical simulations (FDTD) of the currents induced on an EUT (metal box with a rectangular aperture on one side) in both a free-space and TEM-cell environment. The figure of merit for comparing the two cases will be based on the total current difference. We primarily considered the effect of the box size relative to the metal wall separation. As the box size increases relative to the wall separation, the effect of the walls on the induced currents also increases. The question of how large the EUT may become before this difference becomes too large, is of interest to the standards community and other TEM-cell users.

Simulation Procedure

The approach is to compare the currents induced on an identical EUT using two separate simulation models. One that replicates free space, and the other that replicates a modified TEM-cell (parallel-plate waveguide) environment. The EUT considered is a perfectly conducting square box with a rectangular aperture on the front surface facing the incident plane wave, as shown in Figure 1. The tangential magnetic field components along three outside surfaces of the box are stored at each time step for use in determining the induced currents.

Figure 1. Perspective view of EUT.

The free-space environment, diagramed in Figure 2, is modeled by surrounding the metal box with a region of air and truncating the computational volume with an absorbing boundary condition. The TEM-cell model is created by replicating the environment shown within the shaded area of Figure 3. In this model, perfect electrically conducting metal walls are positioned along the upper and lower sides of the simulation model to simulate the upper (or lower) wall and septum (center plate) present in a TEM cell. This model is diagramed in Figure 4. The absorbing boundary remains present along the adjacent sides and ends.

Figure 2. Free-space model.

Figure 3. Cross-section of a typical TEM cell.

Figure 4. TEM-Cell Model.

Figure 5. Distribution of free-space current magnitude at various frequencies.

To investigate the effect of relative EUT size in a TEM cell (h/d ratio), the size (h) of the EUT is held constant while the volume of the TEM cell is varied. This is achieved by varying the separation (d) between the metal walls in the TEM cell model. In all simulations, the EUT is vertically centered between the metal walls.

RESULTS

To analyze the free-space and TEM-cell simulation results, the computed time-domain data were converted into the frequency domain. Figure 5 displays the free-space current magnitude on three outside surfaces of the box at various frequencies. The rectangular aperture is evident on the front face. Similar post-processing was performed on the TEM cell models.

Total Current Difference Measure

The following equation describes an algorithm for quantitatively correlating the free-space and TEM-cell current distributions:

$$\Delta_{cd} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mathbf{x}_i^f - \mathbf{y}_i^t|^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mathbf{x}_i^f|^2} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, \mathbf{x}_i^f is the complex value of the i th component of the tangential magnetic field vector at the frequency of interest for the free-space case, \mathbf{y}_i^t is the corresponding TEM cell value, n is the total number of vector components along one face of the box (i.e., 2 times the number of cells to spatially resolve each face of the box).

Equation 1 was used to determine the correlation between the data from the simulation of various TEM-cell sizes to that of free space. The results of the current difference measure as a function of separation (d) are shown in Figure 6. The three surfaces of the box were analyzed individually. For each TEM-cell model of varying dimension d , correlations at four different frequencies are investigated. For large separations ($d = 1.95$ m and $d = 3.15$ m), the curves indicate the current difference becomes negligible. Over the range of separations, the 100 MHz (circle) and 500 MHz (square) curves indicate a dramatic reduction in current difference between $d = 0.165$ m and $d = 0.3$ m and remain minimal for separations greater than $d = 0.3$ m. The current difference for the 2 GHz (triangle) curve also drops with increasing separation, although the difference is greater along the bottom surface (Figure 6c). Significant increases in the current difference are evident in the 1 GHz (diamond) curve, at separations of $d = 0.3$ m, $d = 0.6$ m, $d = 0.9$ m, and $d = 1.2$ m. A vertical line is included in Figure 6(a-c) to represent the position along the x-axis when $h/d=1/3$ corresponding to the 1/3 rule [1]. Significant increases in percent difference are still evident when $h/d < 1/3$ ($d > 0.45$ m).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. Current difference for $h = 0.15$ m on the (a) front, (b) side, and (c) bottom surfaces of the box.

Interactions of a Periodic Structure

The significant increases in current difference observed at certain wall separations can be explained as the result of interactions with a periodic structure. Using the method of images, the metal walls can be removed and the resonance can be recognized as a consequence of an incident field upon an infinite array of images (see Figure 7). At resonant frequencies, the electromagnetic field distribution surrounding the box is significantly altered from that of free space. This indicates that, at resonant frequencies, the currents induced on an EUT in a TEM cell would be perturbed from that of a free-space environment.

An integral equation formulation of an object in a parallel-plate waveguide is presented in [2]. This formulation shows that a resonance occurs when $d = m\lambda$, where d is the separation of the metal walls, m is a positive integer, and λ is the wavelength of the corresponding resonant frequency.

Figure 7. Equivalent periodic array using the method of images.

Total Current Difference vs. Frequency

Simulating additional TEM-cell geometries of various separation (d) may be useful in better determining the precise location and number of spikes observed in the 1 GHz curve. However, due to the considerable time required for simulation and post-processing, the addition of more data points in the curves above is not practical. If the phenomenon observed at 1 GHz is due to a resonance of a periodic structure, then the effect of the periodic geometry will be highly frequency dependent. A way of obtaining better resolution, without further simulation, is to compute the current difference over a range of frequencies for a fixed TEM cell ge-

ometry. Since the transformation of the time-domain data in to the frequency domain reveals its frequency dependence for numerous frequencies, greater resolution can be obtained by correlating the current flows of the free-space and TEM-cell geometries over a range of frequencies.

The current difference between the free space and specific TEM-cell models over the frequency range of interest produced the results shown in Figure 8, which used separation distances of $d = 0.45$ m, $d = 0.6$, $d = 0.75$, and $d = 1.2$ m in (a-d) respectively.

The results in Figure 8 show that for a specific TEM-cell geometry, increases in current difference occur at multiple frequencies. The spikes in the current difference plots diminish in magnitude and spacing in frequency as the separation distance (d) between the metal walls in the TEM model is increased. Examining the results of Figure 8, the spikes occur at the harmonics of a fundamental determined by the

separation distance (d) between the metal walls (i.e., $d = m\lambda$). For example, the separation distance (between the metal walls) for the TEM-cell model used in Figure 8(c) was 0.75 m. In free space, a wavelength of 0.75 m corresponds to a frequency of 400 MHz. This agrees with the results of Figure 8(c). A slight increase is observed at 400 MHz, and the large spikes occur at upper harmonics of this frequency (0.8, 1.2, and 1.6 GHz, etc.). Simulation of additional TEM cells of various sizes confirmed this resonant behavior.

Effect of EUT Size on Resonance

The effect of the box size on the resonance is examined to verify that the resonance is due to the separation distance of the parallel walls, and to determine its effect on the resonance. In the following simulations, the total wall separation is maintained at $d = 0.75$ m and three EUT sizes are

Figure 8. Current difference versus frequency for separations of $d = 0.45$ m, $d = 0.6$ m, $d = 0.75$ m and $d = 1.2$ m in (a-d) respectively for $h = 0.15$ m.

investigated: $h = 0.075$ m, $h = 0.15$ m, and $h = 0.3$ m.

The results are displayed in Figure 9. In this figure, cross-sectional slices of the z-component of the electric field are displayed within the plots of current difference for the various EUT sizes. The plots of current difference indicate that the EUT size has the effect of altering which harmonics resonate, but does not influence the fundamental resonant frequency (400 MHz). These results reinforce the theory that the resonance is determined by the wall separation. It is also seen that the size of the EUT affects the heights of the resonant spikes. The closer the EUT is to the walls, the more coupling exists between the EUT and the metal walls that will perturb the currents from those of free space.

Figure 9. Cross-sectional slice of the z-component of the electric field and the plot of current difference for a fixed wall separation of $d = 0.75$ m and EUT sizes of $h = 0.3$ m, $h = 0.15$ m, and $h = 0.075$ m, in (a-c) respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The motivation of the work presented is to examine the performance of a TEM cell for EMC immunity testing. For the TEM cell to be a viable alternative for high frequency testing, the electrical "stresses" induced on an EUT should be comparable to those induced if the test is conducted in a free-space environment. To examine the performance, an identical EUT is modeled in a modified TEM (parallel-plate waveguide) and a free-space environment. The effect of relative EUT size with the cell is also investigated.

The currents induced onto the EUT in both environments were examined. The total current difference measure was used to determine the correlation of the currents induced on the EUT. The correlation results indicate that at certain frequencies, a resonance in the TEM cell model is altering the currents induced on the EUT from those of a free-space environment. The frequencies for which a resonance could occur was found to be determined by the wall separation d (i.e. $d = m\lambda$). The size of the EUT determines the amplitude and which resonant modes become excited. Resonant frequencies were found to occur even when $h/d < 1/3$.

Future work should determine the influence that an angled septum (e.g., a broadband TEM cell) cell has on this resonance. In addition, since EMC testing is concerned with performing measurements, the extent to which the resonance influences measurements need to be investigated.

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